

ANALYSIS AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF PUBLIC LoRaWAN NETWORK COVERAGE IN URBAN ENVIRONMENTS***Amankeldiyev M.,****Master student,**Almaty University of Power Engineering and Telecommunications,**Almaty city****Asset N.,****Master student,**Almaty University of Power Engineering and Telecommunications,**Almaty city****Utebergenov I.****Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor,**Almaty University of Power Engineering and Telecommunications,**Almaty city***Abstract**

This study presents an analysis and performance evaluation of a public LoRaWAN network deployed in the urban environment of Köthen, Germany. The research focuses on assessing network coverage and communication reliability under real outdoor conditions using different radio transmission parameters. An end device based on an Arduino Mega 2560 and a Dragino LoRa GPS Shield was configured and connected to The Things Stack (TTS) to transmit georeferenced test packets from multiple measurement points across the city. The experimental evaluation considered key communication metrics, including Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), and Packet Delivery Rate (PDR), for several spreading factors from SF7 to SF12 and different transmission power levels. Based on the collected data, coverage heatmaps were generated to visualize the spatial distribution of signal quality and identify stable, weak, and marginal reception zones. The results show that higher spreading factors significantly improve coverage and delivery reliability, while lower transmission power reduces network performance, especially in obstructed urban areas. The findings provide practical insights into the optimization of public LPWAN deployments and can support future planning of LoRaWAN infrastructure in urban environments.

Keywords: LoRaWAN, LPWAN, urban coverage, RSSI, SNR, packet delivery rate, The Things Stack, IoT.

Introduction

The rapid development of the Internet of Things (IoT) has created a growing demand for wireless communication technologies capable of supporting large numbers of low-power devices over wide geographic areas. In many modern smart city, industrial, agricultural, and environmental monitoring applications, conventional short-range wireless technologies such as Wi-Fi or Bluetooth are not suitable due to their limited communication distance and relatively high energy consumption. At the same time, cellular solutions may provide wide coverage, but they are often associated with higher infrastructure costs and increased power requirements. For this reason, Low Power Wide Area Network (LPWAN) technologies have become an important area of research and practical implementation.

One of the most important configurable parameters in LoRaWAN is the Spreading Factor (SF), which determines the trade-off between communication range, data rate, transmission time, and receiver sensitivity. Higher spreading factors generally improve signal detectability and increase achievable range, but they also increase time-on-air and reduce transmission efficiency. In addition, transmission power has a direct influence on the strength and reliability of the uplink signal, especially in areas with partial obstruction or weak line-of-sight conditions. For this reason, the combined analysis of spreading factor and transmission power is essential for optimizing LoRaWAN performance in practical deployments.

This study focuses on the analysis and performance evaluation of a public LoRaWAN network in the city of Köthen, Germany. The objective of the research is to investigate how different radio transmission parameters influence signal quality, communication reliability, and spatial coverage under real outdoor urban conditions. For this purpose, an end device based on an Arduino Mega 2560 and a Dragino LoRa GPS Shield was configured to transmit georeferenced test messages through a public gateway connected to The Things Stack network server. Measurements were carried out at multiple locations across the city, and the received packets were analyzed using key performance indicators such as Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), and Packet Delivery Rate (PDR).

The practical significance of this work lies in its contribution to the planning and optimization of public LoRaWAN infrastructure. By visualizing the collected data in the form of coverage heatmaps and comparing the results for different transmission settings, it becomes possible to identify areas of strong and weak reception, determine the most effective communication modes, and evaluate the limitations of the current deployment.

First, the hardware platform, network setup, and onboarding process are described. Then, the methodology of data transmission and field measurements is presented. After that, the collected data are analyzed through heatmaps and communication metrics. Finally, the main results are

discussed and recommendations for improving LoRaWAN coverage in urban areas are provided.

2 The experimental part

2.1 Device configuration and network onboarding

The experimental study was carried out in the city of Köthen, Germany, to evaluate the performance of a public LoRaWAN network under real urban outdoor conditions. A Kerlink Wernet Station gateway was used as the network infrastructure element. The gateway operated in the EU863–870 MHz frequency band and was configured according to EU868 regional parameters.

As an end device, an Arduino Mega 2560 equipped with a Dragino LoRa/GPS Shield was used. This hardware platform enabled both LoRaWAN communication and GPS-based location tracking during field measurements. The LoRa transceiver was connected to the Arduino Mega through the SPI interface, while additional control and interrupt pins were assigned for proper radio operation. The GPS module was used to obtain the coordinates of each measurement point. The pin mapping between the Arduino Mega 2560, the Dragino shield, and the LoRa module is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The pin mapping between the Arduino Mega 2560 and Dragino shield

Table 1.

Pin mappind between Arduino Mega 2560, Dragino Shield v1.3 and LoRa BEE v1.1

Interface	Arduino Mega 2560	LoRa Bee v1.1	Quectel L80 (GPS module)	Description
SPI	D51	MOSI	-	Data from Mega to Radio
SPI	D50	MISO	-	Data from Radio to Mega
SPI	D52	SCK	-	Timing/Clock Signal
SPI	D10	NSS	-	Chip Select (Radio On/Off)
Control	D9	RST	-	Radio Reset
Interrupt	D2	DIO0	-	TX/RX Done Interrupt
Interrupt	D6	DIO1	-	Timeout Interrupt
Interrupt	D7	DIO2	-	Frequency Hopping
UART1	D19 (RX1)	-	TX	Receive data from Bee/GPS
UART1	D18 (TX1)	-	RX	Send data to Bee/GPS

For network integration, The Things Stack (TTS) was used as the LoRaWAN server. It provided packet reception, device management, and storage of metadata such as RSSI, SNR, timestamp, and gateway information. In this project, the end device was activated using the Activation by Personalization

(ABP) method. This method was selected because it ensured a simpler and more stable connection during repeated field experiments, especially when the device was frequently restarted at different measurement locations.

Fig. 2. LoRaWAN system Architecture

2.2 End Device Program Structure

The end device firmware was developed on the Arduino platform for LoRaWAN data transmission and GPS data acquisition. Its main function was to read the current coordinates, form the payload, and send uplink packets to the network server.

The transmission process was implemented using the LMIC library, which controlled LoRaWAN

communication and radio parameter configuration. During the experiment, the firmware sequentially applied different transmission settings, including several spreading factors and transmission power levels. The workflow of the program is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. End device workflow and measurement sequence

The general operation of the firmware consisted of initialization, GPS data acquisition, payload preparation, packet transmission, and repetition of the measurement cycle.

3 Results and outcomes

3.1. Comparison of coverage in different directions

The directional analysis of the measured data showed that the LoRaWAN coverage in Köthen was

not uniform. The communication range differed significantly depending on the direction from the gateway location. The best results were obtained in the eastern direction, where packets were successfully received at a distance of about 2.2 km from the gateway. In contrast, the maximum range in the western and southern directions was limited to approximately 1.0 km (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Comparison of coverage in different directions

As shown in Table 2, the eastern side of the city demonstrated the largest coverage distance, while the western and southern sides showed noticeably shorter communication ranges. These results confirm that

gateway placement and surrounding obstacles have a strong influence on LoRaWAN coverage in real urban conditions.

Table 2

Maximum communication distance in different directions

Direction	Maximum distance, m	Latitude	Longitude	RSSI, dBm	SNR, dB
West	991	51.755649	11.945697	-124	-4.8
East	2190	51.754416	11.991777	-124	-16.8
South	984	51.746359	11.962151	-122	-5

3.2. Influence of spreading factor on network coverage

The analysis of the measurement results showed that the spreading factor had a strong influence on the coverage performance of the public LoRaWAN

network. At lower spreading factors, such as SF7 and SF8, stable communication was mainly observed in areas close to the gateway. In these cases, the coverage remained limited, and the signal level decreased more rapidly in distant parts of the city.

Fig. 5. Coverage comparison for spreading factor 7 and 8 at TX Power(Transmission power) 14dBm

With increasing spreading factor, the communication range and signal stability improved. Configurations from SF9 to SF11 provided a wider

coverage area and more reliable reception in urban zones with partial obstruction.

Fig. 6. Coverage comparison for spreading factor 9/10/11 and TX power 14dBm

The best overall result was achieved with SF12 at 14 dBm, which demonstrated the largest coverage area and the highest reliability in weak-signal regions. This

configuration allowed packets to be received from the most distant points and showed the best performance in marginal urban areas.

Fig. 7. Spreading factor 12 and TX power 14dBm

As shown in Fig. 7, the gradual increase in spreading factor resulted in a visible expansion of the coverage area. This confirms that higher spreading factors improve receiver sensitivity and make

LoRaWAN communication more robust in complex urban environments.

3.3 Overall results of the study

Table 3

Summary of the main experimental results

Parameter	Main result
Best coverage direction	East side of Köthen
Maximum range	About 2.2 km
Lower coverage directions	West and South, about 1.0 km
Best spreading factor	SF12
Best transmission setting	SF12 at 14 dBm
Effect of lower TX power	Reduced coverage and weaker signal
Main influencing factors	Gateway placement, spreading factor, transmission power, urban obstacles

Table 3 summarizes the main findings of the study. The best overall performance was achieved in the eastern direction. This can be explained by the gateway installation conditions: the antenna was placed near a window on the fifth floor of the dormitory building, and the window was oriented toward the east side. As a result, signal propagation in that direction was less obstructed, while the west and south directions were more affected by the building structure and surrounding urban obstacles.

4 Conclusion

This study presented an experimental evaluation of a public LoRaWAN network in the urban environment of Köthen using an Arduino Mega 2560, a Dragino LoRa/GPS Shield, a Kerlink Wirnet Station gateway, and The Things Stack as the network server.

The results showed that spreading factors 7 and 8 provided stable communication mainly in areas close to the gateway, where the signal conditions were more favorable. Spreading factors 9, 10, and 11 demonstrated improved coverage and more reliable reception in wider urban areas, indicating better resistance to attenuation and partial obstruction. The best overall result was obtained with spreading factor 12, which provided the widest coverage area and the most stable communication at the most distant measurement points.

Overall, the obtained results confirm that practical LoRaWAN performance in urban environments depends strongly on spreading factor selection, gateway placement, and surrounding obstacles. These findings can be useful for further planning and optimization of public LoRaWAN deployments.

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